

Ultra Low-Power Rail-to-Rail Voltage Comparator in 65 nm CMOS Technology

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Abstract—The paper addresses a re-design and parameter analysis of a *current-mode* rail-to-rail voltage comparator with power consumption in nano-watt range across all PVT corners. The comparator design was done in general-purpose 65 nm CMOS technology with the nominal power supply voltage of 1.2 V. The circuit design needs to function properly in industrial temperature range that is from $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The rail-to-rail input voltage range is achieved without employing two differential pairs and also without an internal voltage biasing circuitry. Furthermore, the design process can be easily automated by means of calculation spreadsheet and employing g_m/I_D design methodology. The presented comparator has been analyzed for robustness and accuracy across all process and temperature corners using post-layout extracted netlist, and some parameters were also investigated through Monte-Carlo analysis. The power consumption does not exceed $1\text{ }\mu\text{W}$ in the worst-case scenario, however in typical PVT conditions, it remains below the first third of nano-watt range. The circuit also contains enable signal to minimize the power consumption down to leakage level when the circuit's function is not required. The topology itself, exhibits a promising potential for further research, since it can also work in ultra low-voltage regime thanks to only two stacked transistors.

Index Terms—Low-Power, Comparator, CMOS, Rail-to-Rail, Energy Harvesting

I. INTRODUCTION

The ever-growing demand for battery-powered electronic devices on the market is shifting the design considerations of integrated circuits towards the low-power and low-voltage domain and required silicon area of the designed circuit might no longer be a number one priority. On-demand Internet-of-Things solutions also motivate engineers and researchers to investigate the field of energy-harvesting units, which provide and manage power supply voltage harvested from an ambient energy source [1]–[3]. For obvious reasons, such systems require minimized quiescent power consumption as a key parameter. The analog and mixed-signal integrated circuit design in advanced nano-scale CMOS technologies has become very challenging even for experienced engineers and researchers, and almost all designs using process nodes below 90 nm employ some kind of calibration circuits or post-processing trimming to compensate the influence of process variations [4]. The emerging CMOS technologies (5 nm or 3 nm nodes) offer higher levels of integration, an unprecedented performance per area in digital systems, better efficiency and

many other advantages. However, from analog point of view, the quality and parameters of circuit components are not always improving with technology advancement. Let us just mention the increased leakage currents, voltage headroom, worse device mismatch, device threshold voltage shift due to aging, overall variability of process parameters and last but not least, the overall price per chip die. The aforementioned facts represent one of the reasons why analog and mixed-signal circuits are preferably still being designed in mature bulk CMOS processes (130 nm and lower) [5], [6].

Our project involves mixed-signal IC design in 65 nm CMOS technology, which would manage and control the energy harvesting unit and deliver regulated output voltage with maximized efficiency. The presented ultra low-power voltage comparator (a prime example of mixed-signal circuit) will be implemented in regulation loop in power management block and in analog-to-digital converter (ADC) as a part of complete System-on-Chip (SoC). The original idea of the proposed rail-to-rail comparator topology lies in the double cross-coupling and absence of traditional differential pairs and their biasing circuitry [7]. The main design constraint, as expected, is the internal power consumption. However, the process variations and device mismatch are of considerable concern, as well. The proposed topology is also capable of proper functioning with lowered power supply voltage, since it requires saturation voltages for only two MOS devices in series. The down-side to this comparator design, are its dynamic parameters. With such a low current flow through the circuit branches, one can expect the maximum operational frequency in tens of kHz. Naturally, depending on the load capacitance. Furthermore, the dynamic parameters are a function of input voltage conditions, since the comparator works in so-called current-mode. Another design constraint was eliminating the need for fuse trimming (e.g. input offset voltage or current consumption). For the given CMOS technology, this represents a real challenge and it might infer an implementation of calibration or digital trimming circuitry [8].

The paper is organized as follows. The first part describes the proposed comparator topology. The second section discusses the achieved simulation results using extracted post-layout netlist. The final chapter concludes the paper along with our intended future research.

Fig. 1. The proposed topology of rail-to-rail analog core along with the device dimensions.

II. ULTRA LOW-POWER RAIL-TO-RAIL COMPARATOR

The addressed comparator consists of two main blocks – analog core and digital control block. The analog core is responsible for processing the input voltage into rail-to-rail range and generating the *difference* signal. The digital block would, in turn, generate binary output based on the difference signal and enable function. The schematic diagram of the analog comparator core is depicted in Fig. 1.

One can observe a complete symmetry between the circuit sides. The first cross-coupling is present at the axis of the circuit, at nodes named *diff* and \overline{diff} . The second cross-coupling is applied at the circuit input. This step introduces the rail-to-rail feature, which will be described in detail later. Let us discuss the left-hand side of the circuit only. Transistors $M1$, $M2$ and $M3$ form a unity current mirror. Their gates are disconnected from the rest of the circuit by a transmission gate (tgate) and pulled to V_{DD} when the comparator is disabled. Devices MN_{in+} and MP_{in+} act as voltage-controlled current source. The input voltage is translated to drain current defined by the transfer curve of respective devices (hence, the current-mode). The rail-to-rail range is achieved by employing both transistor types in the input branch and cross-coupled biasing by the input signal. Transistors $M4$ and $M5$ also form a unity current mirror and reverse the direction of the current flow. Devices MPU and MPD serve as pull-up and pull-down switches, respectively, to cut-off the transistors in current mirrors and to ensure defined potential in nodes *diff* and \overline{diff} when the comparator is being disabled.

Complete small-signal model of the analog core is depicted in Fig. 2. Due to cross-coupling of the input signal, we have to analyze the whole circuit despite its overall symmetry. The non-inverting input of the comparator was fed the small-signal, while the inverting input was biased with DC source as a reference voltage.

The simplified analytical definition of voltage amplification in node *diff* is expressed in Eq. (1). The equation relies on “reasonable” analog design of devices with minimized output conductance, while transconductance being several orders of magnitude higher. Naturally, the given equation is accurate

Fig. 2. The complete small-signal model of the proposed analog core.

only if all transistors are saturated.

$$A_{V_{diff}} \approx \frac{\left[\frac{g_{m3} \cdot g_{mMN_{in+}}}{g_{m1}} + \frac{g_{m9} \cdot g_{m7} \cdot g_{mMP_{in-}}}{g_{m10} \cdot (g_{mMP_{in-}} - g_{m8})} \right]}{g_{ds3} + g_{ds9}} \quad (1)$$

The equation also reveals that in order to maximize the voltage gain in the output nodes, the output conductance of cross-coupled transistors should be minimized, while the transconductance of input devices and cross-coupled devices should be maximized.

The second main building block is the digital output latching circuit and the final inverter, which is responsible for shaping the output signal for given capacitance load. The enable signal is processed by the control block, which also acts as anti-cross protection circuitry. Catastrophic cross-conduction has been observed during the design phase when the power supply voltage became rippled. This scenario is likely with on-chip energy harvesting systems. The controlling block has been described in Verilog and synthesized with focus to minimize both leakage power consumption and number of gates.

The buffers processing the input signals *diff* and \overline{diff} are custom-designed circuits using analog simulations and fine-tuned to amplify the transient input signal while minimizing the current draw.

III. POST-LAYOUT SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we will discuss the achieved post-layout simulation results using so-called corner analysis and also Monte-Carlo scenarios. The most basic parameter of any voltage comparator is arguably its transfer characteristics. We analyzed our design using the reference voltages at the half of the power supply range and 10 mV from the power rails to verify the rail-to-rail function. The described test scenario

Fig. 3. The output latch along with the control logic.

was simulated in all PVT combinations and the resulting waveforms are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Transfer characteristics in various PVT conditions.

One can observe correct function in all simulation corners. Furthermore, the waveforms overlap each other in their transition region with offset voltage in a few units of mV.

The correct way of verifying the input offset voltage, however, is to perform a number of Monte-Carlo simulations with process variations and mismatch included. We set up 100 random simulations for each temperature limit, as well as the room ambient temperature. The input signals consisted of DC reference voltage (with the value of 10 mV, 0.6 V and 1.19 V) connected to the inverting input, and a slow triangle voltage connected to the non-inverting input. In this way, 1800 individual input offset values from two output edges we obtained. The resulting voltage offset values were plotted as a histogram in Fig. 5

One can observe a normal distribution, which is expected for correctly working comparator circuit. The average value of $V_{offset} = 1.27$ mV and standard deviation of $\sigma = 2.55$ mV with $N = 1800$ samples in the population represents a very good result for given technology, and taking into account that

Fig. 5. Monte-Carlo analysis of the input offset voltage for both output edges and various operating temperatures and voltage reference values.

the design does not contain any kind of calibration or trimming circuitry or fuses.

Another crucial parameter in our project is the quiescent power consumption. The worst-case scenario for the power consumption in our topology, is when the input voltages are both high. Hence, we set up the Monte-Carlo scenario with $V_{REF} = 1.19$ V and again, slow triangle waveform at the input with measuring and averaging the current draw required for two output toggles in both directions of the voltage sweep. After that, we calculated the value of average power consumption. The results of described analysis are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Monte-Carlo analysis of power consumption at various temperatures with calculated average value.

Again, one can observe three normal distributions with calculated average value for each temperature. The highest power consumption is recorded at $T_{AMB} = -20$ °C, which is an

interesting fact indeed. However, power consumption value in any case, does not exceed 1000 nW by a considerable margin. As we mentioned earlier, the limitations caused by lowered power consumption are linked to the dynamic parameters of the proposed comparator topology. Fig. 7 depicts the results of Monte-Carlo simulations for each output edge. The simulations were performed at ambient temperature, as well as temperature limits with $C_{LOAD} = 25$ fF. The reference signal was set to a half of V_{DD} and the frequency of input digital signal was $f = 20$ kHz.

Fig. 7. Propagation delay for various reference voltages and PVT corners.

Considering the rising output edge, the standard deviation remains stable across all temperature settings and the shift of average value remains within an acceptable level. The falling output edge exhibits higher levels of average delay values and also higher dispersion of simulated results at low temperature limit. The maximum operational frequency of the proposed comparator remains in tens of kHz, which is satisfactory for our application. However, the increased standard deviation at low temperatures is worth closer investigation in case of more critical applications.

IV. CONCLUSION

We have presented a novel design of rail-to-rail voltage comparator in 65 nm CMOS technology. The main design constraint was the internal power consumption and minimized input offset voltage without a need of digital calibration or trimming. The physical dimensions of the circuit are $25 \times 17 \mu\text{m}$, which equals to $425 \mu\text{m}^2$ of required silicon area. The rail-to-rail feature is achieved without employing two differential pairs but rather by cross-coupling of the input transistors. The extensive investigation of the crucial circuit parameters using post-layout netlist have confirmed a robust voltage comparator capable of withstanding process variations in 65 nm process and with expected worst-case power consumption less than 850 nW. However, under nominal PVT conditions, the circuit requires only about 100 nW. The

input offset voltage analysis resulted in average value of 1.27 mV with the standard deviation of 2.55 mV after $N = 1800$ iterations across the whole voltage and temperature ranges. The rail-to-rail input range was successfully verified in all PVT corners as well. The propagation delay predicted by Monte-Carlo simulations for each output edge remains in units of μs with loading capacitance similar to an on-chip application. The maximum frequency of the presented comparator design is therefore limited to kHz range. The proposed topology, however, can be designed for high-speed applications, as well. In such a case, one would increase the current draw in the analog core, which will increase the slew rate capabilities.

The novel topology has been proven as a working concept for ultra low-power rail-to-rail voltage comparator capable of working also in low-voltage conditions. Thanks to its simplicity, absence of internal biasing circuitry, the transistor sizing can be automated using g_m/I_D approach.

Our future research includes insertion of digitally controlled hysteresis, deeper investigation of low-voltage capabilities and laboratory measurements of fabricated prototype chip samples.

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